

RE-IMAGINING EDUCATION FOR 21ST CENTURY LEARNERS IN THE POST – PANDEMIC WORLD

DR. SHAULI MUKHERJEE
meetingdrmukherjee@gmail.com
Adamas University, India

ABSTRACT

There is an urgent and pressing need to re-imagine and redefine education to suit the needs and demands of an ever changing and constantly unfolding volatile, uncertain, complex and ambiguous world. A complete mind-set shift is required to re-imagine education and learning that will essentially suit the learning needs and demands of the present generation of youths. Our current education system still continues to promote a one size fits all educational structure which needs a complete transformation. In keeping with the essential characteristics of Generation Z in terms of them being entrepreneurial, independent, impatient along with a burning desire to create a visible and tangible difference in the world, there has to be a paradigm shift from an overtly structured and rigid framework of education to a more personalized, stress-free, fulfilling, happy and productive educational structure backed up by the recent advancements in the field of emerging technologies in education. As progressive and futuristic educators, we must wholeheartedly embrace the benefits of a fast-emerging technology embedded teaching - learning ecosystem.

Keywords: educators, 21st century learners, post – pandemic world